

TECHNOLOGICAL ADOPTION READINESS OF MICROENTERPRISES IN SAN FERNANDO, CAMARINES SUR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19145714>

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the technological adoption readiness of home-based microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur by examining their current operational status, technological challenges, readiness levels, and training needs. Using a descriptive research design, data were collected from 21 microentrepreneurs through questionnaires, Likert-scale assessments, interviews, and observations of their actual financial, marketing, and production practices. Results revealed that microenterprises continue to rely on manual production, limited equipment, and traditional marketing approaches, leading to inconsistent product quality, restricted market reach, and slow workflows. Although financial assistance is available, resource gaps such as insufficient equipment, unstable raw material supply, and limited technical knowledge remain substantial. Technological challenges were most evident in financial management, where many operators struggled with digital payment systems, accounting tools, and electronic record-keeping. Marketing challenges included low digital literacy, limited experience in social media promotion, and minimal participation in e-commerce platforms. Production challenges involved high equipment costs, lack of training, and continued dependence on labor-intensive manual processes. Readiness levels showed moderate willingness to adopt technology for financial management and marketing, but low readiness in production, indicating uneven technological adoption across business functions. Overall, findings show that while microentrepreneurs are open to technological integration, adoption is constrained by cost barriers, limited skills, and inadequate support systems. The study developed the TARA Guide (Technology Adoption and Readiness Assistance), a simplified, step-by-step framework offering beginner-friendly tools in financial

management, digital marketing, and production. The Guide is recommended as a practical intervention to support gradual and sustainable technological adoption among home-based microenterprises.

Keywords: *digital adoption, financial management, home-based microenterprises, marketing management, production management*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, globally, technology has continued to revolutionise the manner in which businesses are conducted. The increasing trend has been to systematically incorporate at the enterprise level and across several business processes including marketing, communication, and production processes digital tools, regardless of enterprise size and organization structure. There are still, however, a significant number of small and microenterprises that are struggling to shift into online platforms and automated operational systems. Economic factors like poor internet connectivity, expensive equipment and inadequate digital capabilities still limits the technological adoption of microenterprises. These limitations got even more effective during the COVID-19 pandemic, with enterprises that had an established digital system being more responsive. Most others, on the contrary, failed to cope with the situation and were abandoned. Many empirical research articles have repeatedly revealed that rural-based businesses are one of the most significantly harmed by technological shifts, simply because of a lack of resources, support structures, and a stable digital infrastructure, Creswell & Creswell (2018); World Bank (2021).

Considering it through the prism of the Philippine context, the issue of technology adoption seems even more evident. In spite of the fact that the proportion of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in the business sector of the country is quite significant, most of them still use traditional and manual operational procedures. Even with the government intervention programs like Go Negosyo Act (Republic Act No. 10644) and the creation of Negosyo Centers, there remains a barrier like high costs of technology, low levels of digital literacy, and lack of awareness of digital platforms, especially at grassroots, Department of Trade and Industry [DTI] (2022); Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], (2023). The latter is especially true in the local scene of San Fernando, Camarines Sur, where structural and technological constraints are still a persistent issue that defines the operation of the enterprises and limits the opportunities to implement digital integration in a systematic way. Although these enterprises are crucial to the local economy, most of them work with a small number of resources and little exposure to digital tools, which limits their technological integration abilities. The early signs show that there is still reliance on manual production processes, no far-reaching markets, and no extensive use of technology in marketing, bookkeeping, and communication with customers, ERIA (2019); World Bank (2021). Against these conditions, this research paper evaluates the technological maturity of home based microenterprises in Camarines Sur, in San Fernando, the operations of the enterprise, the level of technology challenge they are experiencing and their readiness to embrace

technological development in the most important functional areas. The study in the end aims to offer a rationale behind the development of suitable interventions that can facilitate slow, feasible and viable technological integration among home-based microenterprises.

The importance of this study lies in the fact that technological preparedness has emerged as a more and more crucial factor of survival, development, and sustainability of microenterprises, and especially those that are located in rural and resource-cut-off settings with institutional constraints and limitations. The ability to determine their gaps in technologies enables small business owners to make more informed decisions that would enhance productivity, increase their market footprint, and enhance financial management. In the case of the local government units and the Negosyo Center, the results can be used as a guide to create better training programs and support services. The results can also be utilized by national agencies such as the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) in the promotion of digitalization efforts by MSMEs. Along with the practical advantages, the research also establishes its mark in the existing bodies of research related to digital preparedness and rural entrepreneurship by highlighting the importance of local contexts in the general discourse, World Bank (2021).

Overall, the constant rise of technology in business underscores the susceptibility to rural home-based microenterprises that are unskilled and lack the resources to remain updated. Although national initiatives are driving digital transformation not every community is able to keep in line with it. There are many micro-entrepreneurs in San Fernando who are tied to the traditional systems and have very little digital exposure. This gap highlights that there is a necessity to conduct selective, context-dependent, and empirically based evaluation that analyzed the capacities, the structural constraints affecting technological adoption among home-based microenterprises. This study will help facilitate the transition to digital inclusion, improve business resilience, and help the local economic development to be sustainable by recognizing their strengths, limitations, and unique needs, ERIA (2019); Asian Development Bank (2021).

Research Objectives

Generally, this study evaluated the technological readiness of home-based microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur. Specifically, it aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Analyze the current status of home-based microenterprises in terms of production challenges, market access, access to resources, government support, and marketing strategies employed.
2. Identify the technological challenges encountered by home-based microenterprises in the areas of financial management, marketing management, and production management.
3. Evaluate the level of readiness of home-based microenterprises in adopting technological innovations in financial management, marketing management, and production management.

4. Develop a comprehensive framework in the form of a simplified step-by-step guide to support the technological readiness of home-based microenterprises.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive mixed-methods research design to generate both quantitative and qualitative data and to examine the technological readiness of home-based microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur. Qualitative descriptive research is suitable in the investigations that need to reflect some aspects of real life circumstances, conditions, and perceptions without controlling variables, to be discussed by Creswell and Creswell (2018). The given strategy can be arranged in the livelihood-based and community environments where the business functions in natural and daily conditions. Microenterprises at home are not formal and are usually influenced on the household routine, restricted resources, and individual decision-making. Given the subjectiveness of these conditions and the realities they are subjected to depending on the context, a qualitative-descriptive framework will enable them to present their lived experiences in a more precise and meaningful way.

With the research design, the researcher was able to investigate significant areas of the microenterprise business such as production practices, market access, technological issues in financial management, marketing and production, and general readiness of microentrepreneurs to use digital tools in the present study. It also contributed toward formulation of interventions of training based on real conditions as opposed to generic assumptions. The research employed the semi-structured interviews, open-ended questionnaires, and Likert-scale survey to guarantee that the information was gathered extensively. This mix of approaches allowed the qualitative-descriptive design to help create a detailed analysis of technological preparedness and the complexity of the circumstances of home-based microentrepreneurs in the municipality.

The major research tool was the questionnaire of a structured questionnaire in five main sections. In the first part, the profiling was conducted through a checklist that was modified to obtain demographic and business related data, including age, gender, years of operation, product type, capital size and connection to the digital devices. The second part was a measure of the current business position of the respondents in the context of business challenges that include production, the availability of the market, source, government assistance and marketing strategies. The third part established technological issues in financial management, marketing, and production in a checklist. Part four determined the willingness of the respondents to embrace the technological innovations in financial management, marketing, and production, through a Likert scale; that is, 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The fifth section determined the perceived training requirements of the respondents on the aspect of technology adoption. In line with further enriching quantitative results, the questionnaire covered some open-ended items that enabled the respondents to discuss their issues, knowledge of digital tools, and the training areas that they felt they needed to be trained on. These qualitative answers

gave deeper understanding of the situation in the microenterprises, and led to the formation of the practical, context-specific training interventions.

The research was carried out in the Philippines in San Fernando, Camarines Sur, where a large number of households have home-based microenterprises, especially these businesses that deal with food processing including production of vegetable chips. Twenty one (21) home based microenterprise operators acted as respondents. The researcher used purposive sampling method in selecting the respondents but the sampling method is suitable where the researcher needs respondents with certain characters that pertain to the research aims. This was to make sure that only those people who had direct roles in the operations of home based microenterprises, especially in the production, marketing and simple financial management were incorporated and therefore the data reflected the technological issues faced in this sector appropriately.

The following criteria were applied to make sure that respondents were qualified to participate in the researcher study: (1) they owned or operated a home-based microenterprise; (2) they were engaged in food production or other livelihood activities; (3) were operating on a small scale with minimal capital and less than nine workers; and (4) were in the municipality of San Fernando in Camarines Sur. The demographic profile revealed that majority of the respondents were women, aged 41 years and above, and at least high school education. Most of them were not well exposed to the digital tools and had uneven access to reliable internet connection, which is a character that rural-based microentrepreneurs in the area have.

The inclusion criteria were put in place to ensure that the study did not lose focus. These were: (1) medium and large business, (2) microenterprises that are not located in San Fernando, (3) business owners who do not conduct their business at their households and (4) market players who refused to participate or were not available at the time of data collection. All these parameters were to make sure that this study focused specifically on the part of the microenterprise operators where the concept of technological readiness can be most relevant and useful.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents in Terms of Demographics and Business Characteristics

Profile Variable	Frequency	%	Rank
Age			
Below 40 years	2	10%	3
40–59 years	10	48%	1
60 years and above	9	43%	2
Total	21	100%	
Gender			
Male	6	29%	2
Female	15	71%	1
Total	21	100%	
Educational Attainment			
Elementary Graduate	4	19%	2
High School Graduate	13	62%	1
College Level/Graduate	4	19%	2
Total	21	100%	
Type of Business			
Food Production (chips)	21	100%	1
Total	21	100%	
Years in Operation			
1–3 years	4	19%	3
4–6 years	11	52%	1
7+ years	6	29%	2
Total	21	100%	
Farm/Production Size			
Below 1 hectare	15	71%	1
1 hectare and above	6	29%	2
Total	21	100%	
Employees			
1	2	10%	3
2-5	15	71%	1
6+	4	19%	2
Total	21	100%	
Technological Exposure			
None	11	52%	1
Basic (mobile, computer)	10	48%	2
Total	21	100%	
Internet Access			
With internet	5	24%	2

No internet	16	76%	1
Total	21	100%	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Current Status of Home-Based Microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur

This part addresses the existing situation of home based microenterprise in terms of production, market access, access to resources, government assistance, and marketing plans.

Production Challenges

Table 3 indicates that one of the issues encountered in production is a lack of equipment, and the frequency of this problem was the highest, 20. Failure to get skilled labor was the highest cause of 18 respondents and lack of raw materials was the highest at 17. The reason that was ranked as the least problematic challenge was the issue of processes that are inefficient, which one respondent also mentioned. These findings are the allocation of the production troubles faced by home based micro businesses of production. All in all, the statistics prove that one of the most frequently mentioned issues is equipment, skills, and resource limitation.

This could be attributed to the fact that the same tools, used at household level, were still in use, which restricts productivity and reliability in the manufacturing of vegetable chips. Most of the operators might not be able to get access to affordable and suitable equipment that has been set up to support small scale production. This could also be due to the fact that in most cases, microentrepreneurs are not given technical training and they are left to rely on manual labor. The absence of reports on the inefficient processes could be because of the tendency to be conversant with the old routines that they are not aware are restrictive. The other assumption is that the shortages of raw materials may be caused by the seasonal gap between supply and weak connections to local suppliers.

Table 3. Current Status of Home-Based Microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur

Parameters	Frequency	Rank
Production Challenges		
1. Limited equipment	20	1
2. Lack of skilled labor	18	2
3. Lack of raw materials	17	3
4. Inefficient processes	1	4
Market Access		
1. Local (within the town)	21	1
2. Regional (within province)	5	2
3. National	4	3
4. International	3	4
Access to Resources		
1. Funding	21	1
2. Equipment	18	2
3. Labor	7	3
4. Raw materials	2	4
Government Support		
1. Financial assistance	21	1
2. Training	18	2
3. Marketing Support	3	3
Marketing Strategies Used		
1. Word of mouth	21	1
2. Social media	5	2
3. Direct selling	1	3

These results suggest that home-based microenterprises have serious limitations to production because of the lack of tools and technical expertise. It can be deduced that these limitations do not allow them to produce more or produce products with the same quality. This also indicates that they cannot be able to extend their market since their production systems are sluggish and labor intensive. One can also assume that in the absence of adequate equipment and training of skills, microentrepreneurs will still be susceptible to mistakes and discrepancies. In general, a conclusion can be drawn that their production preparedness is low because their technological basis has a gap.

The results are in line with the literature whereby the micro and home based enterprises tend to find it challenging with production owing to inadequate equipment, skill, and technology. Gamundo et al. (2020) observed that micro and small businesses in Laguna cannot afford high cost of operation, and strict terms of lending because they cannot afford modern production equipment, as was the case with the respondents in San Fernando who continue to use a simple equipment and manual labor. Similarly,

SERP-P, Alonzo et al. (2021) pointed out that inefficient production due to insufficient machinery and training related to production results into poor productivity and inefficiency as is the case in this research. Barroga et al. (2019) also found that the use of manual methods is prevalent among microenterprises, which are supported by the state but still lack exposure to technologies and strong abilities to keep up with the advanced equipment, reflecting the reliance of the respondents on the traditional, labor-intensive processes. Pacubas et al. (2025) also pointed to technological constraints, lack of digital with low technological awareness, as the reasons that decrease the transition to digitized production systems, similar to the slow technological adoption in the production problems in San Fernando. On a global scale, Juniarti (2021) discovered that small enterprises tend to be slow to implement new production technologies, believing that they are complex, expensive, and do not have technical support, which also corroborates the fact that the technological gap is here to stay because the respondents continue to work with simple tools and inefficient processes.

It is suggested that microentrepreneurs should use the Production Management Section of the TARA Guide that specifically deals with the challenges outlined above by offering a straightforward, easy-to-follow steps that help to use inexpensive tools. The Guide presents low priced equipment like pastry cutters, pasta systems, dehydrators, and temperature regulated fryers- all clearly selected to address the issues of the small equipment and haphazard manual processing. The TARA Guide supports the shift of the operators who use the manual process of slicing, sun-drying, and uncontrolled frying to the more efficient, uniform process using illustrated workflow and operating instructions that are easy to follow. It also contains general trouble shooting guidelines, safety precautions and an effective decision checklist to enable the user prioritize equipment depending on the budget and production requirement. With the help of this well-organized, open-source tool, microentrepreneurs will be able to achieve efficiency of production, uniformity of products, and competitiveness in the long term respectively.

Market Access

Findings prove that the local market is the most visited as 21 respondents recognize it as the major selling place. There are 5 respondents in the regional market and 4 respondents in the national market. The smallest in terms of visited is the international market with just 3 respondents saying that they are exposed to it. These findings represent the market reach distribution among microenterprises. In general, statistical data demonstrate local high concentration and inaccessibility to larger markets.

These could be because they produce small volumes thus they are not able to fulfil their clients outside their town. Microentrepreneurs are not always ready to go beyond the narrow circles, such as online methods. This can also be attributed to the fact that they do not have digital marketing skills which would enable them to access regional or national buyers. The other assumption is that they could view bigger markets as expensive or risky because of logistics or competition. This could also be attributed to lack of awareness on programmes that lead to the growth of markets.

Based on these findings, the microenterprises are still reliant on local customers and local referrals. It can be derived that they will have limited chances to scale as long as their digital presence is not more visible or wide-reaching marketing efforts. The inability of capability is now a greater obstacle to the market growth than the quality of the products. One can also assume that their lack of involvement in bigger markets also has an impact on their long-term sustainability. In general, their market access can be broadened only in case of the enhancement of technological competencies.

The fact that this firm can use local markets that were detected in this study is also consistent with the findings of limited market presence of micro and home-based enterprises as gathered in the past. Francisco et al., (2024) found that the Philippine SMEs find it hard to enter the larger markets due to the lack of knowledge on doing business, the lack of human resources capacity, and the high quality and certification requirements these have which are the reasons explaining why most of the respondents in San Fernando still concentrate on the local customers. The World Bank (2019) also emphasized that most microenterprises are inadequately integrated into the network, trade fairs, and business associations and, as a consequence, have little exposure to new buyers and market information, which correlates with the small roles in the regions, country-nation, and international networks indicated in the statistics. ERIA (2019) also found that a significant part of microenterprises in the ASEAN countries are not aware of the digitalization efforts organized by the government which would help them receive access to the online market. This confirms the observation that participants in this research are currently clinging more on the physical markets and town-based markets as opposed to online stores. Further, ERIA (2019) outlined the limitation of microentrepreneurs due to inadequate transportation infrastructure, expensive freight, and unprofessional distribution intermediaries to the served markets outside the local region- equally the logistic challenge that probably restricts San Fernando operators to nationwide or global expansion. Combined, these findings support the finding that the highly localized nature of the market coverage of the respondents is a subset of a larger trend of limited market accessibility of micro and home-based firms.

Microentrepreneurs are advised to apply the Marketing Management Section of TARA Guide, which was made exclusively to aid them to grow beyond local markets. This part will give easy and stepwise instructions on how to create Facebook Pages, posts in Marketplace, take product pictures, and write promotional captions - modules which are taken to alleviate the negligence of digital marketing ability. Guide also contains information how to open Shopee and Lazada seller accounts in case the operators want to access regional and national customers. Weekly posting schedule sample templates and branding layout examples can help users keep up with the online presence routinely. With these well-organized, user-friendly tools, microentrepreneurs can slowly transition to a more global promotion through local sales to technology-enhanced market interaction.

Access to Resources

As indicated in Table 3, the most ready source of resource is funding with 21 respondents having indicated the same. The second is equipment which has an 18 respondent, and the third is labor which can be readily found by 7 respondents. Accessibility of resource (in this case, raw materials) is the least reported with only 2 respondents reporting it. These findings introduce the rate of availability of resources among microenterprises. Overall, there seem to be easy access to financial resources, and scarce resources of materials and human resources.

Such findings may be caused by the existence of microfinance initiatives that enable business people to have access to capital. Operators can be short of knowledge on how to convert capital into operations as sources of funds are available. The scarcity of raw materials can either be a result of haphazard supply chain in the rural setting or result of seasonal harvests. The other assumption is that access to equipment is also not easy since businessmen are not aware of what tools can be used and which are affordable. It could also be due to the fact that where labor is supplied primarily includes family members instead of an employed workforce, hence the limited availability of work force. Based on this finding, financial support is not a sole measure of increased business operation. It can be inferred that the constraints of resources in terms of equipments, labor and raw materials can hamper the optimal utilization of financial aid. This implies that microenterprises lack the knowledge or networks required to convert capital to better production systems. One can conclude that unbalanced distribution of resources impedes the growth and makes them less prepared to adopt the technology. All in all, capacity-building and not funding is needed to access resources.

The observation that the funding is easily available compared to other resources, whereas equipment, labor, and raw materials are scarce, echoes the past research on the issue of resource limitation among microenterprises. As Raquiza, (2021) discovered, microenterprises have too small a number of opportunities to acquire formal bank loans due to the absence of acceptable collateral, uneven financial documentation, and irregular operations and have to resort to using informal lenders with high interest rates. This explains why fund may be inadequate or even unstable even in cases where funds are availed, but long-term upgrading is required. Consistent with the findings of the Philippine Commission on Women (2023), fluctuating supply chains and the use of intermediaries make procurements more expensive and make the availability of raw materials unpredictable, which is interpreted by the few respondents who identified high levels of reliable access to raw materials. It was observed that most microenterprises are ill equipped in terms of capital and technical skills to embrace modern manufacturing technologies and therefore could not upgrade their equipment; in line with the disparity between funding options and the continuously restricted accessibility to production tools that were found in this study Loo (2023). As reported by Barroga (2025), a limited level of awareness of automated production technologies and a perceived prohibitive price do hinder MSMEs to engage in digitization, and this is why uneven access to equipment and other technology-enhancing facilities among the respondents remains a significant problem. Moreover, Sarita (2025) found that limited resources and poor technology

planning help diminish the effectiveness of support programs like SETUP and Shared Service Facilities, which also supports the result that financial support does not ensure adequate labor and equipment or raw materials to start, manage, or expand a home-based microenterprise in San Fernando.

It is recommended that microentrepreneurs use the Financial Management Section of the TARA Guide to convert available funding into organized, technology-supported financial systems. The Guide provides Excel templates for budgeting, expense tracking, costing, and inventory planning—tools that teach operators how to allocate funds strategically for equipment, materials, and labor. By following step-by-step instructions for recording sales and expenses, microentrepreneurs can evaluate whether they have sufficient cash flow to invest in production tools or raw materials. The Guide also introduces simple worksheets for planning procurement cycles, which can facilitate reducing material shortages. By integrating these tools, microentrepreneurs can utilize their financial resources more effectively and sustainably.

Government Support

The table shows that the most commonly received government support is financial (21 respondents). Training programs are listed below with 18 respondents indicating they participated in these. Marketing support is the most negative with only 3 respondents saying they have access to marketing support. These results show the availability of government support for microenterprises. Overall, the results indicate more emphasis is placed on assistance to finance and training with little marketing support. These results could be attributed to government programs which favor livelihood funding over long-term enterprise development. A lack of access to marketing-focused initiatives that could strengthen business visibility may be the case with microentrepreneurs. The fear of low frequency of marketing support may also be attributable to the weak capacity of LGUs to offer special assistance. Another presumption is that the bureaucratic requirements may make it difficult for microentrepreneurs to receive an extensive support. It may also mean that operators are unaware of the programs that already exist.

From these results, there are not enough government supports that will suffice to the full operational needs of microenterprises. It can be gleaned that despite provision being made for financing and training, marketing has been overlooked. This implies that microenterprises may not be getting holistic support addressing the dual objective of the efficiency of operations and growth in sales. It can also be concluded that the lack of regular help may restrict the long-term business sustainability. Overall, it can be inferred that microentrepreneurs need better and integrated support programs to be accessible to them. In 2019, the Office of the Vice President of the Philippines gave direct support to microenterprises in San Fernando in the form of funds, equipment, and facilities. However, with this initiative, no other office or agency continued this sort of assistance causing operators to be left without assistance. The results on government support - whereby most of the respondents received financial assistance and training but very little marketing support, are consistent with evidence on how MSME programs are designed and implemented across the Philippines. The World Bank (2019) reported that despite

the various support programmes, including financing facilities and training, there is often poor coordination and weak targeting of the support programmes, which would leave out or only serve informally operating or home-based microenterprises to a limited extent. DTI's (2024) MSME Development Plan also advocates digitalization and productivity. However, the implementation at the local level is still uneven, due to low LGU capacity and varying digital readiness - consistent with the pattern of mixed support found in San Fernando. ERIA (2019) also mentioned that information relating to digitalization initiatives by government agencies is often not reaching the microentrepreneurs, and because of this, they tend to have low participation during seminars, access to technology, and capacity building conferences. This is consistent with the experience of lack of follow-through after initial financial support reported by the respondents. In addition, Abaquita et al. (2024) found that bureaucratic procedures and extensive documentary requirements discourage microentrepreneurs from availing of incentives under laws such as the Barangay Micro Business Enterprise (BMBE). As a result, many home-based businesses remain unregistered and are unable to benefit from the policy perks designed to support their growth to the fullest. Philippine Institute for Development Studies PIDS (2025) further demonstrated that AI and high-tech programs tend to reward more digitally capable and medium-sized enterprises and the home-based microenterprises will be excluded. Together, these studies support the conclusion that there is some financial and training assistance for San Fernando microenterprises, but government assistance is limited, sustained and marketing-focused.

It is recommended that government units consider incorporating the TARA Guide into their current microenterprise programs to enhance their support to cover a more comprehensive array of issues and make the support more accessible. The TARA Guide provides pre-made modules on financial management, marketing and production - where LGUs, DTI, TESDA and cooperatives can hold structured, skills-based training in response to the needs identified in this study. By making printed copies of the TARA Guide available during seminars, LGUs can ensure that microentrepreneurs have a permanent reference that they can use after training sessions. In addition to this, by applying the Guide as a standardized training tool, agencies can provide consistent, simplified, and local support. Through this integration, microentrepreneurs are granted not only with finance but also with the technical capacity for sustainable growth.

Marketing Strategies Used

The table results indicate that word of mouth is the most commonly used marketing strategy as 21 respondents reported it. Social media is the second highest with 5 users and only 1 of the respondents use Direct selling. These results show the marketing practices distribution of microenterprises. In general, the data suggest extensive reliance on traditional marketing. The results indicate that digital and direct selling strategies are not popular. These results may be from the fact that microentrepreneurs are used to informal and interpersonal marketing. It implies that the digital literacy level of people may be low, which may prove to be a limitation to the confidence they would put into using online platforms. The low use of social media could also result from lack of equipment, or an unstable internet connection. Direct selling may be in short supply because of

transportation problems or lack of foot traffic. Another presumption is that the operators may not have the knowledge of creating compelling digital promotional content. From these findings, microentrepreneurs rely to a great extent on personal networks to access customers. It can be deduced that their poor engagement is limited to digital which confines their expansion outside their immediate community. This hints that they may be leaving opportunities to access new market segments or younger market segments. Without the ability for digital marketing their competitiveness is still limited. Overall, growth cannot do without marketing modernization.

The domination of marketing of word of mouth and the low assumption of use of social web and individual selling sold seems close to the same description found in the existing literature. Mia et al. (2024) noted that a lot of MSMEs adopted social media platforms including Facebook and Instagram during the Covid-19 pandemic but did not have a long-term digital marketing strategy and stable connectivity neither with required skills in the platform management, which is similar to the low number of respondents in this study which used social media. Cueto et al. (2022) also found that while digital platforms provide young Filipino entrepreneurs with a way to connect to their customers, a lot of them have deployed online branding, content creation, and data analytics skills, which explain why home-based microentrepreneurs from San Fernando still rely prominently on their personal networks and word of mouth. Pacubas et al. (2025) referred to the shift to digital servitizations, such as online catalogues and messaging-based customer support, but noted that microenterprises that lack access to and technical capacities with the internet find it difficult to sustain these digital offerings and this is consistent with the nature of the respondents with minimum engagement in more advanced digital selling strategies. Sarita (2025) emphasized on the failure of microenterprises in planning, execution, and sustainability of digital campaigns, which is similar to the lack of structured online marketing with the respondents. Internationally, Capral et al. (2021) found lack of willingness of SMEs to fully adopt e-commerce due to concern for costs, online security and trust in digital platforms; this could be compared to the cautious limited home-based microentrepreneurs online marketing behavior in San Fernando. These connections confirm that the dependence on traditional word of mouth promotion by respondents is part of a wider trend of incomplete and patchy digital marketing adoption among microenterprises.

It is recommended that microentrepreneurs use the Marketing Management Section of the TARA Guide, which outlines simple steps that can be easily implemented and used to start digital promotion. This section has guides on how to create Facebook Pages, figure out how to design social media posts, take good pictures of products, and a guide on how to write good captions - all skill-sets necessary to equip operators with the basics of marketing. The Guide also features templates for weekly posting schedules and for branding layouts so that users can ensure a consistent online visibility. Step-by-step directions for establishing a store(s) with Shopee and Lazada further facilitate the process of selling from the traditional market to online stores. By utilizing these easy-to-follow tools, microentrepreneurs would be able to start building on digital presence gradually and reach a larger number of customers, beyond word-of-mouth marketing.

Apart from TARA Guide, microentrepreneurs are also advised to avail themselves from free online learning platforms that offer simple-to-undertake digital marketing courses. Platforms like Coursera, LinkedIn Learning, YouTube Learning, TESDA Online Program (TOP), Canva Design School and DTI's free virtual seminars provide accessible, no-cost training, which can be used to develop improved skills. These platforms provide bite-sized useful lessons on topics such as content creation, social media strategy, branding and online selling - filling the gaps in digital skills identified within this study. By using the structured, localized approach of the TARA Guide in combination with the free global resources available online, the microentrepreneur is able to develop a greater capability for marketing and can confidently grow beyond word-of-mouth marketing.

Technological Challenges of Home-Based Microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur

This section introduces and explains the technological problems of home-based microenterprises, namely, in the financial management, marketing management and production management.

Financial Management

In this section, the researcher provides the technological issues that home-based microenterprises encounter in operating their financial matters, especially with regards to the utilization of accounting software, digital payments solutions, and e-records management software.

Table 4. Technological Challenges in Financial Management of Home-Based Microenterprises

Parameters	Frequency	Rank
High cost of tools	16	1
Lack of knowledge or training	15	2
Not needed for the business	4	3

As shown in table 4, the most important technological challenge in the financial management is the high cost of tools, with 16 respondents reporting it to be the highest. This is closely trailed with a scarcity of lack of knowledge or training which is cited by 15 respondents. But the most basic obstacle is the thinking that the business does not require financial technology which is believed by the fewest amount of respondents who were four. These findings introduce the profile of financial technology obstacles among micro entrepreneurs. On the whole, the statistics show that the main impediments to the process of using digital financial tools are cost and expertise shortages. This implies that a majority of the operators are yet to become conversant or comfortable with the idea of using online tools to take control of their business funds. Still, many people rely on the

usage of the handwritten notebook and the use of the manual ledger in order to enter the data on the daily transactions. Though this traditional form is easy, easy to manage and accessible, it is subject to human error, time consuming in updating and the financial institutions or the government agencies do not perceive this as a good evidence of income. Moreover, small operators are deterred to use digital-based accounting software because of its cost and apparent complexity. Meanwhile, the lack of the knowledge of e-wallet platforms inhibits their capability of serving customers who are keen on transactions without cash.

Individual lack of exposure, training and confidence in use of digital systems primarily causes the absence of technological gap in financial management. This state of affairs inhibits the modernization of the micro enterprises in terms of keeping track of the performance, gaining access to credit and assistance programs that presuppose formal financial reporting. It may also depend on age since older operators would be less confident using mobile apps or software. This generation gap may however be overcome by incorporating younger family members who would take up the data entry and payment transaction roles.

The results are fairly comparable to the literature, as it reveals that microenterprises are severely inhibited in technological fronts in financial management. According to Martin et al. (2023), responses indicated that fragmented financial systems and manual operations do not allow SMEs to move to the digital accounting industry; this situation is reflected by the fact that the respondents still use handwritten ledgers. As it was highlighted by the Asian Development Bank ADB (2022), rural MSMEs do not trust digital tools and have issues with affordability, which is also in line with the necessity of addressing high costs as the main concern by respondents. Necessary limitations in the digital literacy and outdated systems were also mentioned in both studies by Pacubas et al. (2025) and Barroga et al. (2019), and it coincides with the reported shortage of training and familiarity in this study. Juniarti (2021) also proves the findings by mentioning that minor businesses find digital tools confusing. Therefore, the findings of the study contribute to existing evidence and prove that the barriers to financial technology adoption include the lack of skills, cost, and complexity. Microentrepreneurs are urged to adopt the Financial Management Section of TARA Guide that has easy-to-use Excel templates and step-by-step instructions of how to record the sales, expense, and costing. There are also screenshots, arrows, and simplified instructions in the Guide that help overcome the fear and allow users to use the spreadsheet even first-time users. It also provides a lesson on downloading and organizing GCash transaction histories, making operators make digital payments and digital records related. The visual examples and preformatted templates in the Guide lead the users not to create files to pre-establish the foundation and develop a sense of confidence over time. Using this built in module, the microentrepreneurs can not only break the barriers of cost and knowledge but also bridge the gap of using hand written notebooks to well organization digitized systems.

Marketing Management

The section describes technological issues associated with home-based microenterprises in the field of marketing management, such as product marketing restrictions, digital marketing provisions, the social media, and the involvement in online selling platforms.

Table 5. Technological Challenges in Marketing Management of Home-Based Microenterprises

Parameters	Frequency	Rank
Lack of knowledge or training	15	1
Lack of equipment (computer/internet access)	11	2
Cost concerns	11	2

Table 5 revealed that the most commonly reported challenges of technology in marketing management is lack of knowledge or training, which was reported by 15 respondents. This is followed by lack of equipment and cost concerns with 11 respondents for each. These results provide the distribution of impeding digital marketing adoption. On the whole, the results reveal a low digital preparation in marketing practices. The results show that most microenterprises are still relying on traditional marketing techniques such as local fairs, referral from the neighborhood, and walk-in customers. While these strategies are familiar and thus culturally ingrained, they provide limited market reach and visibility. Many respondents indicated little to no experience in using digital marketing tools. While social media sites like Facebook come for free, e-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Lazada charge for e-commerce transactions between two to five percent, which is a discouragement for small entrepreneurs who have tight profit margins. These cost issues, and a lack of knowledge regarding online marketing, account for the reluctance to use digital approaches despite the potential benefits.

Limited technological readiness in marketing limits home based microenterprise from growing beyond their local communities. And their dependence on the old ways of sales hampers them from being as competitive as possible, especially against businesses that use the digitised ways of selling to tap the markets of the region of the country, or even the nation. The generational divide in technological comfort can also be a reason for this limitation; for example, older entrepreneurs might have difficulty working through online tools if they are not technologically savvy, while younger members of the family are often more able to adapt if given the proper training. As a result, these enterprises are not as visible on the digital marketplace and they have limited their sales and long term sustainability.

The results that lack of skills, equipment, and cost issues impede digital marketing are consistent with the review of literature. Mia et al. (2024) and Cueto et al. (2022) mentioned that problems MSMEs often experience when using social media are dealing with them, branding and digital content, consistent with respondents in this case mentioned knowledge gaps. Pacubas et al. (2025) highlighted the importance of unstable access to the internet affecting the implementation of digital strategies, which is compatible with the lack of equipment cited above. Capral et al. (2021) noted that small businesses are reluctant to enter e-commerce because of perceived risks and costs and these factors can be the reason why many respondents are unwilling to adapt to other platforms such as Shopee or Lazada. Therefore, the results agree substantially with the already available studies that digital marketing readiness remains low among the microenterprises.

It is suggested that microentrepreneurs use the Marketing Management Section of the TARA Guide that teaches them how to establish Facebook Pages, design product posts, take good photos and write interesting captions. The Guide includes pre-populated templates for branding, weekly posting schedules and product layouts, which make marketing tasks easier and less tedious. It also provides step-by-step tutorials on how to set up stores on Shopee and Lazada so that they will no longer be afraid of the processes and fees on the platform. Through its format that is easy for beginners the Guide minimizes dependency on technical expertise and enables users to practice digital marketing according to their own schedule. By following these modules, the microentrepreneurs can gradually gain confidence and visibility online.

Production Management

This section describes technological challenges faced by the home based microenterprises in their production processes where challenges are addressed on the equipment, skills as well as the use of modern production technology.

Table 6. Technological Challenges in Production Management of Home-Based Microenterprises

Parameters	Frequency	Rank
High cost of equipment	19	1
Lack of technical skills	19	1
No need for additional technology	1	2

Table 6 indicates that the top ranked technological challenges in production include high cost of equipment, lack of technical skills, 19 respondents and 19 respondents respectively. There was only one respondent who said there is no need for additional technology. These results show the distribution of production related technological barriers among microentrepreneurs. The development of skills and

shortages in equipment are major concerns, the data shows. In general, the implementation of production technology is facing significant limitations.

The results show that a large number of home based microenterprises cannot afford modern machinery and still depend more on manual labor and household tools to carry out production. The lack of training also limits their capacity to introduce new technologies that can increase efficiency and consistency of their products. As a result, their production processes are still time consuming, labor-intensive and prone to quality inconsistencies. For example, the vegetable chip producers will often use knives for slicing, in place of a pastry cutter and ordinary pots for frying, instead of temperature-controlled fryers or dehydrators. These practices - while cost-effective - limit their productivity and scalability. Limited access to affordable equipment and technical knowledge seriously impedes production efficiency among the home-based enterprises. Without the right tools and the training to use them, operators risk slow outputs, inconsistencies in quality and struggling to meet an increase in demand. This technological gap means that they are unable to compete with more advanced producers who use semi-automated systems. As a result, product consistency and competitiveness in the market are remaining huge challenges for small scale operators.

The technological challenges identified in production, of which some are high cost of equipment, and lack of technical skills, are found in the existing literature in direct correspondence. Salcedo et al. (2019) reported that micro food processors are still using the manual slicing and frying methods as concluded in the usage of knives and household pots from the interviewees. DTI (2021) highlighted that the costs for the equipment lead to the suppression of the adoption of technology, which is consistent with the top challenge identified. Juniarti (2021) also mentioned that production technologies are viewed by small businesses as complex and costly, which also corroborates the results. Pacubas et al. (2025), also Loo (2023) reiterated the low digital literacy blocking MSMEs adoption of automation. The present results thereby confirm the literature regarding persistent structural barriers to the modernization of production.

It is recommended that microentrepreneurs make use of the Production Management Section of the TARA Guide, which introduces low complexity practical tools in an affordable way suitable for beginners. This section includes step by step demonstration pages for the use of pastry cutters, pasta makers, dehydrators and temperature controlled fryers - areas of equipment directly linked to their top difficulties of cost and skills gaps. The Guide also describes workflow improvements including uniform slicing, controlled drying and precise frying temperature to improve product consistency. It contains easy to implement troubleshooting tips, safety reminders, and a decision checklist to help users decide on equipment they should adopt first depending on their budget. And by sequentially engaging in these modules, microentrepreneurs can gradually transition from manual production processes to more efficient and consistent production processes without the overwhelming technical demands.

Readiness of Home-Based Microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur to Adopt Technology

This section shows how ready home-based microenterprises are to adopt technology in their operations, especially in financial management, marketing management, and production management. It indicates how prepared the respondents are to utilize digital tools, online platforms, common shared facilities, and modern equipment to boost business efficiency and competitiveness.

Financial Management

This section assessed the degree of preparedness of home-based microenterprises to embrace technology in managing their finances especially the application of digital payment systems, simple accounting tools, and electronic methods of financial track.

As seen in Table 7, the use of digital payment systems is the most appropriate indicator of readiness related to financial management (Weighted Mean = 3.10, Moderate Readiness). That is succeeded by budgeting and financial tracking preparedness (Weighted Mean = 3.00, Moderate Readiness). The use of simple accounting tools like excel is the lowest index of readiness (Weighted Mean = 2.90, Moderate Readiness). The levels of preparedness of microentrepreneurs to use financial technologies differ in these results. In general, an average of 3.00 shows that the degree of financial management technology adoption is moderate.

Table 7. Level of Readiness in Technology Adoption for Financial Management

Parameters	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Use of digital payment systems (e.g., GCash)	3.10	MR	1
2. Use of basic accounting tools (e.g., Excel)	2.90	MR	3
3. Budgeting and financial tracking readiness	3.00	MR	2
Mean	3.00	MR	

Legend:

- 4.21–5.00 - Very High Readiness (VHR)
- 3.41–4.20 – High Readiness (HR)
- 2.61–3.40 – Moderate Readiness (MR)

These results could be attributed to the familiarity of the mobile wallets such as GCash that the microentrepreneurs are accustomed to using for their personal money transactions. It goes on to suggest that digital payments are less intimidating because the setting up of digital payments is minimal and there are no requirements of a formal accountancy background in this. The lower preparedness for Excel could be the fact that spreadsheet tools seem complex or overwhelming for the first time user. Another presumption is that operators might not perceive the need for structured accounting immediately, if their businesses are quite small and informal. It could also be the lack of exposure to digital record-keeping by training or community programs. Based on these results, microentrepreneurs are starting to incorporate technology in their financial practices, although only in simple ways that they are familiar with. Their readiness is probably most acute in areas requiring minimum technical skill like e-wallet transactions. This, in turn, indicates that the structured digital record-keeping has yet to be mastered because of low confidence and inadequate training. While they are aware of the usefulness of financial technology, they do not yet feel inclined towards the implementation of more systematic applications such as Excel. Overall, it can be deduced that their financial readiness is coming but is incomplete without step-by-step support.

The moderate readiness found is consistent with ADB (2022) which noted that rural MSMEs to a certain extent adopt financial technologies due to skill limitations, and lack of infrastructure. Similar to Loo (2023) and Sarita (2025), respondents in this study show cautious but increasing use of digital tools of all sorts, especially in mobile payments. Parasuraman and Colby's Technology Readiness Index supports the pattern they note: users are optimistic about relative simple tools such as e-wallets but are uncomfortable for more complex software such as excel. Thus, the results confirm the findings from the literature, which recommends that financial technology is used in microenterprises over time in step increments based on complexity and familiarity.

It is recommended for microentrepreneurs to make use of the Financial Management Section of the TARA Guide which addresses these gaps in readiness through simplistic financial tools that are easy to use for financial literacy. The Guide contains pre-formatted Excel templates for sales tracking, recording expenses, costing and calculating weekly profit - this allows operators to make the most of using spreadsheets without having to create files from scratch. Step by step visual instructions help users understand very basic Excel functions so that fear is reduced and confidence is built. The module additionally introduces linking GCash transaction histories to Excel records to bridge the digital payments many people are familiar with, and the structured bookkeeping people may not understand. By following the TARA Guide, microentrepreneurs can move from handwritten notebooks to organizing and supporting their financial systems with technology over time, but at a pace that is comfortable for them.

Marketing Management

In this section, the study addressed the willingness of home-based microenterprises to embrace digital technologies in marketing, such as social media platforms, e-commerce platforms, and digital analytical tools to sell their products.

Table 8. Level of Readiness in Technology Adoption for Marketing Management

Parameters	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Use of social media platforms for promotion	3.00	MR	1
2. Readiness to adopt e-commerce platforms (Shopee, Lazada)	2.90	MR	3
3. Capacity to use digital marketing analytic	2.95	MR	2
Mean	2.95	MR	

Legend:

- 4.21–5.00 - Very High Readiness (VHR)
- 3.41–4.20 – High Readiness (HR)
- 2.61–3.40 – Moderate Readiness (MR)
- 1.81–2.60 – Low Readiness (LR)
- 1.00–1.80 – Very Low Readiness (VLR)

Table 8 shows that the maximum readiness indicator in marketing management is using social media platforms for marketing promotion (Weighted Mean = 3.00, Moderate Readiness). This is followed by the ability to use digital marketing analytics (Weighted Mean = 2.95, Moderate Readiness). The lowest readiness indicator is the adoption of e-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Lazada (Weighted Mean = 2.90, Moderate Readiness). These results show the distribution of marketing readiness of respondents. Overall, the value 2.95 is the average meaning that the level of readiness in the adoption of marketing technology is moderate. These results could be explained by the fact that Facebook is widely used by the many respondents as a means of personal communication. It is suggestive in showing that they are more comfortable with non-structured posting compared to regulated online stores. The low readiness for the adoption of e-commerce may be attributed to e-commerce platforms like Shopee and Lazada requiring extra steps including account verification, listing products and settling seller's fee. Another presumption being that microentrepreneurs might not be confident in negotiating the logistics and delivery systems. Or it could be brought about by limited knowledge of how analytics tools can facilitate them improve online performance.

From the results, microentrepreneurs are willing to make use of simple promotional tools but are not willing to deal with more complicated online selling functions for the moment. It can be inferred that their readiness focuses on known platforms that do not require any technical understanding. This implies that the adoption of e-commerce is still a problem due to the fact of complexity and fear of making mistakes. A lack of support in such an effort could lead them to continue to rely on basic posting as opposed to structured online marketing. It can be deduced that digital marketing readiness is present but at a surface level form of engagement.

The moderate level of readiness in digital marketing is in line with the findings by Mia et al. (2024) who found partial digital marketing adoption among MSMEs. Cueto et al. (2022) also mentioned the lack of digital branding skills, which reflects the low analytics readiness of the respondents. According to Pacubas et al. (2025) unstable internet access as a barrier which also corresponds with respondents concerns of expensive equipment. Capral et al. (2021) mentioned perceived risks and costs of e-commerce adoption, which corresponded to the low readiness for Shopee/Lazada. These connections validate the idea that cost, skills, and confidence are limitations to getting ready. It is recommended that microentrepreneurs utilize the Marketing Management Section of the TARA Guide which was specifically designed to help microentrepreneurs go beyond simple posting to structured, effective digital marketing. The Guide gives step-by-step instructions on how to create Facebook Pages, write captions, design layouts, and take good product photos, that allow the user to professionalize their online presence. It also introduces the simple analytics concepts such as post reach, engagement, and customer response time to enable the operators to interpret the results without confusion. To facilitate the readiness of e-commerce, the Guide also provides illustrated tutorials on how to set up shop on Shopee and Lazada, as well as understanding how much seller fees are and how to manage orders. By using these modules, microentrepreneurs can incrementally transition from the very basic promotion of social media to more elaborate and money-making digital platforms.

Production Management

This section describes the degree of preparedness of home-based microenterprises to the use of technology in production in terms of how willing the businesses are to utilize automated machines, inventory controlling technology, and employing technology to enhance product quality. Table 9 reveals that the readiness index that has been managed best in production management is the level of enhancing the quality of the products with the help of technology (Weighted Mean = 2.65, Moderate Readiness). It is followed by work with automated equipment to enhance the efficiency (Weighted Mean = 2.60, Low Readiness). The least preparedness indicator is preparedness to use technology in inventory management (Weighted Mean = 2.55, Low Readiness). The following are the findings that introduced the distribution of production technology readiness, among the microentrepreneurs. In general, the average of 2.60 demonstrates that the level of the readiness to adopt the production technology is low.

Table 9. Level of Readiness in Technology Adoption for Production Management

Parameters	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Use of automated equipment to improve efficiency	2.60	LR	2
2. Readiness to use technology for inventory management	2.55	LR	3
3. Improving product quality through technology	2.65	MR	1
Mean	2.60	LR	

Legend:

- 4.21–5.00 - Very High Readiness (VHR)
- 3.41–4.20 – High Readiness (HR)
- 2.61–3.40 – Moderate Readiness (MR)
- 1.81–2.60 – Low Readiness (LR)
- 1.00–1.80 – Very Low Readiness (VLR)

The reason for these results may be the awareness of the microentrepreneurs to the minor improvement of the quality of the equipments. While they are aware of possible benefits, they may not feel confident in using tools that seem to be technical or complicated. The poor readiness in the area of inventory management may be due to the existence of large-scale counting or tracking by memory by operators. Another presumption is that the equipment costs discourage experimentation or purchase of new equipment. It could also be the lack of exposure to simple technological alternatives that are in scale with their production size.

The relatively greater preparedness to improve the product quality indicates that respondents are aware that technological instruments can be used to improve uniformity and the number of product defects in this case technology tools such as pastry cutters, dehydrators and temperature-controlled frying pans. However, this interest has not been converted into actual practice given the reliance on familiar manual methods. For example, they still rely on manual techniques such as using kitchen knives to cut raw materials, guessing frying temperature based on their eyesight, or using their eyesight to judge the product's doneness. Inventory management is also managed using notebooks, free sheets or by using the mind, due to which stocks are miscounted or monitoring of raw materials is not consistent. These age-old habits with the manuals create a large gap in the preparedness. While the operators want to work for the improvement of the quality of the products, they are not having the skills, exposure and confidence to switch to the tools that call for handling to even basic technology. Thus, the gap is not only in terms of

a lack of equipment, but also a lack of preparedness to move away from manual to technology assisted production. The low readiness in production is consistent with the literature, which highlights persistent gaps in the adoption of production technology. According to Salcedo et al. (2019) the reliance on manual systems consistent with the use of basic tools by the respondents. DTI (2021) and Juniarti (2021) observed that despite these benefits, high equipment cost and perceived complexity are the main barriers to adoption, which is similar to the results of this study. Tests of low digital literacy and little exposure to automation described by Pacubas et al. (2025) and Loo (2023) were, in fact, the barriers to readiness which resonated in the low scores of inventory and automation readiness. Thus, results confirm the literature on wider adoption of technology in production processes that lags behind financial and marketing technologies.

It is recommended that microentrepreneur should use the Production Management Section of TARA Guide which introduce simple and low cost tools to the beginner. Equipment control guidance This module contains step-by-step instructions on the use of pastry cutters, pasta makers, dehydrators, and temperature-controlled fryers; again equipment used to improve product consistency without being very advanced. The Guide also gives illustrated flow charts which illustrate how minor adjustments in slicing, drying or frying temperature will improve quality. Through these slowly progressive and easily accessible modules, microentrepreneurs can gain confidence to use technology in improving production.

Summary of Level of Readiness in Technology Adoption of Home-Based Microenterprises in San Fernando, Camarines Sur

This section summarizes the overall level of readiness of home-based microenterprises to adopt technology across financial management, marketing management, and production management.

Table 10 summarizes the readiness levels for three domains, financial management (Weighted Mean = 3.00, Moderate Readiness) is the one that is the highest ranking, followed by Marketing management (Weighted Mean = 2.95, Moderate Readiness). Production management is the lowest with a score of 2.60 (Low Readiness). These findings introduce the comparative readiness level of microentrepreneurs to the adoption of technology regarding business functions. The sum of the mean values (2.85) suggests readiness for technology adoption at a moderate level.

Table 10. Summary of Level of Readiness in Technology Adoption

Parameters	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Financial Management	3.00	MR	1
Marketing Management	2.95	MR	2
Production Management	2.60	LR	3

Overall Mean**2.85****MR**

Legend:

4.21–5.00 - Very High Readiness (VHR)

3.41–4.20 – High Readiness (HR)

2.61–3.40 – Moderate Readiness (MR)

1.81–2.60 – Low Readiness (LR)

1.00–1.80 – Very Low Readiness (VLR)

The results of the study seem to indicate that microenterprises are best positioned to adopt technology in financial management, primarily because digital payment systems, mobile banking applications and simple accounting tools are widely accessible, relatively inexpensive and simple to use. Marketing management readiness is also at the moderate level as a result of social media's convenience to promote products and interact with customers without the need for high technical skills of entrepreneurs. In contrast, production management is the most serious technological gap. Microenterprises still use old-fashioned production methods, which include hand-cutting raw materials, old-fashioned frying without temperature control, sun-drying, and hand keeping track of inventory. These manual systems have limitations regarding consistency, scalability and quality control, which have made the switch to automated equipment or digital inventory tools more difficult. The reason of latter under-positivity in production is caused by the higher equipments cost, under technical knowledge and under-awareness of machinery operation and digital inventory systems.

It can be deduced that home-based microenterprises is in a transitional phase in terms of technology integration and they are actively working for the adoption of technological innovations to carry out communication, financial transactions, marketing and promotion of their product, but are still limited in terms of modernisation of backend activities. This imbalance is critical: while the forward development of digital processes in the front end is moving forward, it is up to the use of the technology in production to balance efficiency and permit the full utilization of digital opportunities. The findings are in consonance with the Asian Development Bank (2022), which calls the attention of Filipino rural MSMEs to having "stronger adoption of communication and financial tools but remain in the limited adoption of production-related technologies". Similar conclusions were reported by Gamundo et al. (2020); Loo (2023) & Sarita (2025) who stressed the fact that microenterprises are usually faced with financial and capability-related difficulties to mechanize and technology-driven production. (Parasuraman & Colby's, 2015) Technology Readiness Index also lends credibility to the notion that people may be optimistic about digital tools and limited by perceived complexity and cost, which is consistent with what people in the respondent pool were reporting.

It is recommended that microentrepreneurs work with the whole of TARA Guide with a good mix of modules for financial, marketing and production domains. The financial management tools make it possible for them to develop digital competence fundamentals using excel templates and gcash workflows. The marketing management section builds its ability to reach a wider market with the help of social media posting guides, branding templates, and e-commerce tutorials. The production management module brings low cost tools and step by step demonstrations so as to eliminate the fear and complexity of

using production technology. By utilising TARA Guide as an integrated toolkit, microentrepreneurs can work towards gradually and sustainably building readiness in all three domains. This will guarantee more balanced approach to technological adoption based on the business growth.

Comprehensive Framework in the Form of a Simplified Step-by-Step Guide

This section introduces the specific needs of training of home-based microentrepreneurs in San Fernando, Camarines Sur. It discusses how these needs are the rationale behind the development of a comprehensive and simplified step-by-step guide of The results indicate gaps in financial management technology, digital marketing skills and production technology, which suggest that microentrepreneurs require a structured and easy-to-follow framework, which will integrate some key areas of business operations.

Financial Management

The microenterprises need financial management to monitor their income, expenses, prices, and the overall business performance. Nevertheless, numerous domestic operators keep records manually thereby restricting financial reporting and accuracy. The findings that follow indicate the particular financial management trainings that respondents consider necessary in making them adopt technological tools in their businesses better.

Table 11 shows that the first training need identified as the greatest need in financial management is the combination of training on basic accounting software (Excel) as well as digital payment systems identified by 10 respondents or 48%. Training on Excel only comes second with 6 respondents or 29% while 4 respondents or 19% reported not being in need for training. Only one respondent or 5% asked to be trained in digital payment systems only. These results show the spread of the financial technology trainings needs for microentrepreneurs.

Table 11. Training Needed for Financial Technology Skills

Training Needed	Frequency	%	Rank
1. Training on basic accounting software (Excel) and digital payment systems	10	48%	1
2. Training on basic accounting software only	6	29%	2
3. No training needed	4	19%	3
4. Training on digital payment	1	5%	4

systems only

Total	21	100%
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These results may be attributed to the fact that respondents may have realized that several financial tools work better when used in combination rather than in isolation. It suggests that they like to be trained in a way that shows them the complete process of financial workflow - from recording sales to integrating digital payments and not in bits and pieces. This might also be because many are still dependent on handwritten notebooks and it is difficult for income and expense to be tracked accurately. The low preference for digital payment training alone could be cited as variety in familiarity with GCash but not knowing how to link transactions with digital records. Another presumption is that respondents want guided steps that reduce the fear of committing errors in using it, this may be deduced to mean that microentrepreneurs need structure, integrated financial capacity building and not topic specific financial trainings. It can be gathered that their preparedness is enhanced when financial tools are linked with an easy step by step process. This implies the need for a simplified training framework that will show how digital payments work into the digital records. It can also be concluded that respondents are more benefited from visual and guided procedures illustrating each step of the financial workflow. Whilst it can be inferred overall that the development of a simplified financial guide is essential to improving technological readiness.

The emphasis on combined accounting and digital payment training that people have seems to show support for the findings of Parasuraman (2000) & Davis (1989), who stated that the perceived ease of use and competence serves to increase the willingness of adoption. Similar observed by Pandey (2015); Kotler & Keller (2016), with regard to the positive contribution of financial literacy in improving enterprise growth and there is a justification to be forthright in ensuring that holistic training is carried out. These results are in line with the literature, as integrated, practical training enhances readiness to a significant degree Langdon & Rivera (2023); Montiel & Harris (2023). To meet this identified need, Financial Management Section of TARA Guide should be utilized for integrated financial training. This section includes intro level excel templates for sales, expense, costing. step by step explanation on using GCash, QR codes, linking the transactions to digital records. The guide also contains an oversimplified financial workflow chart on how daily transactions should be recorded. These materials help microentrepreneurs move gradually away from handwritten notebooks and towards structured digital financial systems.

Marketing Management

Digital marketing has become essential for expanding market reach, especially for microenterprises operating in rural communities. Online platforms enable entrepreneurs to access larger customer bases, showcase their products, and remain competitive. However, many respondents reported limited familiarity with these tools.

Table 12. Training Needed for Digital Marketing

Training Needed	Frequency	%	Rank
1. Social media marketing (Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok) and online selling platforms (Shopee, Lazada)	17	81%	1
2. No training needed	4	19%	2
Total	21	100%	

The results provided in Table 12 indicate that the most needed marketing management training requirement is bilateral training on social media service platforms (Facebook, Instagram, Tik Tok) and on online selling platforms (Shopee, Lazada), which are referred to by 17 respondents or 81%. The percentage of respondents who said that they did not need training was only 4 or 19%. These findings provide the digital marketing training needs distribution as well as displaying an overwhelming inclination toward full training. These findings may be attributed to the fact that the respondents had known that digital marketing has the potential to reach out a large number of customers. It implies that they would like to be instructed not only concerning posting, but also using e-commerce sites. This could also be due to the fact that respondents have realized the disadvantages of using word of mouth and Facebook posts only. The other assumption is that the respondents might be confused with the distinction between promotional posting and online selling, resulting in a preference to the integrated training. It also shows fear of making errors in the handling of the online shops with no organization of guidance.

Based on these results, it can be deduced that microentrepreneurs are open to the digital marketing but they need simplified training which is offered on platforms. We can draw a conclusion that preparation becomes better in case the guidelines are provided to show an understanding that various digital tools will complement each other. This implies that a simple and clear tutorial will enable the microentrepreneurs to comfortably use social media and e-commerce. Also required are practical stepwise instructions that would develop autonomous digital marketing abilities. On the whole, a comprehensive marketing framework is required to contribute to adoption.

The demand of digital marketing training is high as evidenced by the discovery of the OECD and ASEAN (2024), it demonstrated that the problems of the rural MSMEs are an important factor in its inability to meet the training requirements. Laudon and Laudon (2020) stressed on the concept that competitiveness is motivated by digital competence; at the same time, Rogers (2003) emphasized that the adoption is lower in cases of complexity- respondents are in need of simple and practical training. In this way, the results prove that rural microenterprises need special training on digital marketing. In order to fulfill this requirement, the Marketing Management Section of the TARA Guide must be the key training material. This section comprises step by step guides on how to

make Facebook Pages, layout construction, product photography and writing captivating remarks. It also gives stepwise instructions on how to create Shopee and Lazada accounts as a seller. The guide has branding templates and weekly posting schedules which are aimed at enabling microentrepreneurs to adopt other regular marketing processes. These streamlined modules enable all microentrepreneurs to move freely into online promotion and e-selling.

Production Management

Technology in production contributes greatly to the enhancing of consistency, efficiency and production- particularly to food processors who usually embrace manual, labor intensive production. The education in this respect can assist the microentrepreneurs to modernize their operations and embrace the suitable technologies.

Table 13. Training Needed for Production Technology

Training Needed	Frequency	%	Rank
1. Training on automating equipment to increase production speed	14	67%	1
2. No training needed	7	33%	2
Total	21	100%	

Table 13 indicates that, the greatest need of training in production management is training on how to automate the equipment to enhance production speed as cited by 14 respondents or 67%. Only seven respondents or 33% felt that no training was necessary. These findings offer the spread of training preference of microentrepreneurs basis on production. It is possible that these are because of the manual production methods and the physical strain and the slow output of these methods. It is a hint that the respondents are aware that equipment would allow for easier collection and hasten the process, yet they are inexperienced with such instruments. The other assumption is that, most of the respondents have watched or heard about their equipment such as dehydrators or slicers, but they have not been adequately demonstrated. The 33% reporting no training requirement may not be quite aware of available technologies or may be fearful of equipment expense. This could also be attributed to the fact that they may not have been exposed to inexpensive and small scale tools that can be used at home.

Based on this, it can be concluded that microentrepreneurs would like to see production modernized but do not have the knowledge and confidence to implement equipment by themselves. It can be learned that preparation is heightened when training is practical, easy, and step-wise. This implies that they can move away on manual with the help of a visual guide. Suitable tools should be offered at an affordable price to

minimize prall; it can be concluded that the simplified production technology guide should be offered so that the practical skills development can occur.

The high interest of the respondents in automation training is also in line with Stevenson (2017), who wrote that production technologies enhance output and consistency. ADB (2022) also documented that rural businesses also use outmoded tools because they do not have access to the latest technologies. The diffusion theory by Rogers also contends in favor of the complexity diminishing adoption, which clarifies why the respondents require training but with a hands-on approach. Therefore, the results confirm that training is an imperative factor that facilitates the adoption of production technology.

Towards fulfilling this training requirement, Production Management Section of the TARA Guide is an instructional manual detailing the operation of inexpensive and small-scaled equipment including pastry cutters, pasta makers, dehydrators, as well as temperature-controlled fryers. This guide consists of workflow graphics, safety alerts and troubleshooting hints that are beginner friendly. These streamlined modules enable the microentrepreneurs to take their time to modernize their production processes without being intimidated. The guide facilitates the safe and uniform implementation of production technologies in a comfortable way.

Figure 3. TARA Guide (Technology Adoption and Readiness Assistance)

The TARA Guide (Technology Adoption and Readiness Assistance) was designed to assist the home-based microentrepreneurs in San Fernando, Camarines Sur, to enhance their financial, marketing and production management practices by availing of clear, practical and easy to use resources. According to the research findings, microentrepreneurs still have a number of problems such as no equipment, lack of digital literacy, a poor web presence, and inability to utilize simple technological solutions. These are obstacles that influence their performance in business and willingness to embrace the new technologies.

The information embedded in the TARA Guide has been developed through the analysis of the research findings, the review of the available digital tools and community level training programs and closely through the analysis of the individual technological gaps that are being faced by microentrepreneurs especially in areas of record-keeping, online marketing and production effectiveness. The analysis of these findings was converted into straightforward templates, step-by-step instructions, and guides that are easy to understand so that the content was focused on the fundamental problems that permeated their daily activities. The name TARA (meaning Technology Adoption and Readiness Assistance) was given on the basis of the intention of inviting microentrepreneurs taking their first steps towards digital adoption by adopting learning that is simple, gradual, and manageable. It mirrors the notion that technology should not be complex and costly, but rather it can be presented in a format of familiar examples, low-cost tools, and simple guidelines that one can follow and that coincide with the current level of skills and the available funds of the microentrepreneurs.

Production of the TARA Guide in the form of a physical and online booklet is necessary to target the microentrepreneurs who have in most cases, limited internet and/or limited exposure to digital and online learning resources. The TARA Guide is also translated into Filipino and Bikol to be available in languages that are more understandable to the microentrepreneurs so as to ensure they are inclusive and culturally relevant. A printed booklet will mean that the guides, templates, and workflow will be available during training and that they can be consulted multiple times as a source of knowledge at home. The need to provide physical materials will be beneficial in gaining confidence as well as closing the generational barrier, particularly, when the younger members of the family are involved in ensuring that technology will be used continuously in the process of running businesses. The spread of the TARA Guide at LGU, DTI, TESDA, school, and cooperative trainings will also advance the level of awareness and aim at promoting a regular engagement in the technology-based programs in the community.

The TARA Guide is centered addressing three key areas in accordance with the needs detected in the study. The Financial Management category provides easy-to-use Excel templates, online payment options, and convenient record keeping systems so that microentrepreneurs have a more precise approach to creating sales, costs, and costing. The Marketing Management section offers instructions on how to use the social media to post, tips on photography of your products and how to build your own e-commerce in easy steps to enable the microenterprises to better their online presence and fight outside

the local markets. Finally, Production Management section features cost-effective, easy-to-use new devices and working manuals that increase product consistencies, velocity, and safety by using small scale technologies. The TARA Guide is a convenient, realistic starting point because of these elements, which allows microentrepreneurs to develop their technological preparedness at their speed. It enables them to progressively incorporate digital and mini technological devices in their day-to-day activities, to facilitate long-term sustainability of businesses, enhance competitiveness, and wider market involvement.

Conclusions

Research Objective 1: Analyze the Current Status of Home-Based Microenterprises

1. **Production Challenges.** Microenterprises are able to maintain the day-to-day operations, but cannot expand the output or the products uniformity as they do not have any equipment and technical assistance.
2. **Market Access.** Their local only market coverage indicates not just a level of production, but also a poor online marketing behaviour that makes them unable to expand outside the community.
3. **Access to Resources.** Interventions such as financial aid do not make microenterprises resource-bound due to the absence of access to equipments, reliable suppliers or skilled labor.
4. **Government Support.** The assistance is still insufficient, and there is a serious deficiency in promotion, digitization, and lifetime mentoring.
5. **Marketing Strategies Used.** Word of mouth is the primary promotional technique that will restrict business expansion and exposure, particularly within a more digitalized market.

Research Objective 2: Assess the Technological Challenges in Financial Management, Marketing Management, and Production Management

1. **Financial Management.** Financial service digitalization is still low due to low skills, confidence, and low-cost tools of microentrepreneurs.
2. **Marketing Management.** The poor access to and limited digital literacy limits microentrepreneurs to transitioning to online promotion or e-commerce.
3. **Production Management.** The cost of equipment and lack of technical expertise is high in impeding production technology adoption as this influences speed and quality.

Research Objective 3: Evaluate the Level of Readiness to Adopt Technological Innovations in Financial Management, Marketing Management, and Production Management

1. **Financial Management.** Readiness exists but is limited to simple tools; structured digital bookkeeping requires further support.

2. Marketing Management. Respondents are willing to promote online but lack stronger digital marketing and e-commerce skills.
3. Production Management. Respondents are least ready to adopt production technology due to resource, cost, and skill barriers.

Research Objective 4: Develop a Comprehensive Framework in the Form of a Simplified Step-by-Step Guide supporting the Technological Readiness of Home-based Microenterprises

1. Financial Management. Microentrepreneurs require a structured approach to understanding financial processes, and the learning design must be simplified, applied, and example-driven rather than heavily theoretical.
2. Marketing Management. Microentrepreneurs require a structured approach to understanding financial processes, and the learning design must be simplified, applied, and example-driven rather than heavily theoretical.
3. Production Management. Production-related learning is most effective when supported by clear visual demonstrations and simplified, safety-oriented instructions that match the constraints of home-based microenterprises.

Recommendations

Research Objective 1: Analyze the Current Status of Home-Based Microenterprises

1. Production Challenges. Microenterprises are also advised to use low-cost small-scale machines/tools such as pastry cutters, pasta machines, dehydrators, and fryers with temperature control that are visible in Production Management Section of the TARA Guide. The Guide includes step-by-step instructions, safety-related notices, and workflow charts which assist the operator in transitioning to semi-automated production at a pace comfortably. This can be assisted by LGUs and DTI by providing equipment-sharing hubs, or purchase on subsidy basis.
2. Market Access. The Marketing Management Section of the TARA Guide that teaches on how to create Facebook Pages, how to enhance product photos, how to write captions, and how to take advantage of features of the Marketplace to boost presence are encouraged to the microentrepreneurs. The Guide has tutorials of Shopee and Lazada, which may assist them with regional and national customers. LGUs can also be of help in connecting them to trade fairs and online selling.
3. Access to Resources. Financial Management Section of the TARA Guide will offer templates of budgeting in Excel, costing sheets, and procurement planning tools which assists microentrepreneurs to have a better budget allocation of financial funds. LGUs and cooperatives should enhance access to raw materials through creating supplier linkages and by setting up community based procurement centers.
4. Government Support. It is also suggested that the LGUs, DTI, TESDA, and cooperatives should consider promotion of the TARA Guide into the official training programs to ensure that financial, marketing, and production issues are always

taught with simple and localized examples. This will guarantee a continuity and fill the existing digital and marketing support gap.

5. Marketing Strategies Used. Microentrepreneurs might use the TARA Guide Marketing Management Section that provides the posting templates and branding layouts as well as the step-by-step visual guidelines of social media promotion. Also, they should be motivated to take free online digital marketing classes at Coursera, Canvas design school, TESDA online program, and online webinars of DTI. These are free sites that have newbie friendly modules which tighten the belt to skills without being costly.

Research Objective 2: Assess the Technological Challenges in Financial Management, Marketing Management, and Production Management

1. Financial Management. Microentrepreneurs are advised to start to work with the Excel templates and GCash guides which are available in the Financial Management Section of the TARA Guide. These templates make it easier to keep bookkeeping and they also aid in linking to the daily sales records to the digital payment workflows.
2. Marketing Management. Marketing Management Section of the TARA Guide have simplified guidelines on how to post, create layouts and establish online stores. The additional education may be acquired through the free web-based courses on Coursera, Google Digital Garage, Meta Blueprint, and TESDA Online Courses.
3. Production Management. The step-by-step demonstrations of the equipment available in the Production Management Section of the TARA Guide are also recommended to the operators so that they know how to operate small-scale tools safely and effectively. There should be shared machineries or subsidies programs by the LGUs, in which the operators can be able to get access to the equipment at minimal costs.

Research Objective 3: Evaluate the Level of Readiness to Adopt Technological Innovations in Financial Management, Marketing Management, and Production Management

1. Financial Management. Microentrepreneurs should gradually adopt the beginner-friendly Excel and GCash templates within the TARA Guide to build confidence in digital financial management.
2. Marketing Management. Respondents should follow the TARA Guide's content creation templates, weekly posting calendars, and e-commerce tutorials as a stepping stone toward full adoption of online marketing.
3. Production Management. The TARA Guide's illustrated equipment guides (pastry cutter, pasta maker, dehydrator, temperature-controlled fryer) offer simple entry points to improve consistency and reduce manual labor.

Research Objective 4: Develop a Comprehensive Framework in the Form of a Simplified Step-by-Step Guide supporting the Technological Readiness of Home-based Microenterprises

1. **Financial Management.** It is recommended that the financial modules of the TARA Guide—covering Excel templates, budgeting sheets, costing tools, and GCash workflows—be officially used during LGU-, DTI-, and TESDA-led financial literacy training programs. Trainers should demonstrate each step in real time to ensure understanding.
2. **Marketing Management.** The Marketing Management section of the TARA Guide should be implemented in community workshops to help microentrepreneurs create Facebook Pages, design product layouts, and set up Shopee/Lazada stores. Trainers are encouraged to utilize the Guide's visual templates and posting schedules to reinforce consistency.
3. **Production Management.** Hands-on sessions conducted by LGUs or cooperatives should adopt the TARA Guide's production demonstrations, which include step-by-step instructions for slicing, drying, and controlled frying. These simplified diagrams help microentrepreneurs safely and confidently apply technological improvements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher was working with integrity and accountability, and within the ethics code of conduct, in order to safeguard the wellbeing and pride of the home-based microenterprise operators within San Fernando, Camarines Sur. Each participant signed an informed consent following the briefing about the purpose, procedures, and possibilities of risks and benefits of the study. The study was voluntary, and the respondents informed that they could pull out in the study without reprisal. Anonymizing all the data collected ensured privacy and confidentiality in that no identifying information (names, locations, business information) was disclosed in any section of the results. The research problem focused on home-based microenterprise operators in San Fernando, Camarines Sur, utilizing a mixed-methods approach involving both quantitative and qualitative data collection. Prior to the conduct of the survey and interviews, permission letters were secured and informed consent forms were distributed to all participants. The researcher ensured that participation was voluntary and that respondents were fully informed of the purpose of the study. Confidentiality and fidelity to the research objectives were strictly observed throughout the data collection process.

The researcher has ensured that there is no conflict of interest that affects the design, data collection and interpretation of the results to ensure that the readers remain informed and trust the study. The using of all the external information was correctly cited in order to prevent plagiarism and to recognize the efforts made by the original source and writers. In addition, the researcher complied with Data Privacy Act of 2012 by utilizing the digital and physical storage, which was locked and could only be accessed by authorized personnel to ensure that all questionnaires, interviews records, and transcripts are secured. Ethical issues were also taken into account during the utilization of AI to

support writing and interpret data. The application of AI was only necessary to structure ideas and refine words in the manuscript. Precautions were implemented to avoid biases and guarantee the correctness and quality of the results. The researcher conducted all the interpretations and conclusions after conducting a manual validation. Such openness would ensure such AI use does not lead to a reduction in academic honesty.

Objectivity and impartiality was upheld throughout the research process. There was no misleading, exaggeration, or biasness in the results and the difficulties that microenterprises encounter were laid out in a respectful and realistic way. Results were reported with fairness and sensitivity and accounted respondent lived experiences without re-branding or being sensational. With these ethical guidelines, the study was able to engage the community it needed to understand and support in a credible, responsible, and respectful manner.

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